

Water, sanitation and hygiene in schools in low- and middle-income countries: the current state of affairs

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Summary

A systematic review of peer-reviewed literature on WASH in schools in low- and middle-income countries was performed. Five databases were used to identify papers published. Sixty-five papers met the inclusion criteria. We extracted and analyzed data considering the Joint Monitoring Programme (JMP) definitions and the normative contents of the Human right to safe drinking water and sanitation. Publications included in this systematic review considered 18,465 schools across 30 different countries. Results indicate a lack of adequate WASH conditions in schools, which hampers the school community to practice handwashing a key strategy to contain the spread of SARS-CoV-2.

KEYWORDS: WASH, Handwashing, Developing countries, Education, Human rights.

1. Introduction

Based on evidence of the benefits of school closures from former influenza outbreaks and as an attempt to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions in the beginning of the pandemic (Viner et al., 2020). At the present time, the reopening of schools has already started, with most of the schools around the world being partially open. In order to support educational institutions during school reopening phases, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched a checklist of protective measures which include and acknowledge the provision of safe drinking water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) as essential to ensure adherence to hand hygiene etiquette and further COVID-19 prevention in schools (Benzian et al., 2020). However, as pointed out by WHO and UNICEF through the WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme (JMP), worldwide and especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), the majority of schools lack the necessary WASH infrastructure to ensure the safety of the school community during the school reopening (WHO-UNICEF, 2017). Despite the recognition of hand hygiene as a key aspect to prevent COVID-19, hitherto WASH interventions are rarely included in the list of structural and environmental measures carried out in the schools to reduce transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Kshnaratne et al., 2020).

To address the insufficient WASH infrastructure in schools in LMICs and consequent implications for students' health, firstly, however, research is needed to identify and describe WASH conditions in LMICs during the COVID-19 pandemic. In order to fill this knowledge gap and also to highlight the importance of WASH in schools, we conducted the first systematic review on WASH in schools in LMICs. We sought to understand:

- What is the situation of water, sanitation and hygiene conditions in schools in LMICs?
- What are the implications of the current WASH conditions in schools in LMICs for the safe reopening of schools during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and for future water-related pandemics?

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2. Materials and methods

The review was conducted in adherence with the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Moher et al., 2009). In April 2021, five databases were systematically searched: PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, African Journals Online (AJOL) and *Literatura Latino-Americana e do Caribe em Ciências da Saúde* (LILACS). Search terms were divided into three blocks – Block 1 (water, sanitation and hygiene), Block 2 (schools and students), Block 3 (low-and middle-income countries). Blocks were combined using boolean operator AND while search terms within the blocks were combined using boolean operator OR. Prior to the screening of titles and abstracts, this systematic review was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42021248831) (PROSPERO, 2022), where more information on the search strategy, inclusion criteria, quality assessment of studies, etc., can be found in more details.

3. Results

Sixty-five papers were included in the review. The results of this systematic review refer to a total of 18,465 schools. The studies took place in 30 different countries, most of them located in Africa (53.3%, n=16), Asia (33.3%, n=10) and less frequently in Central (10%, n=3) and South America (3.3%, n=1). Ethiopia, Nigeria and Uganda were the countries where WASH in schools was more frequently assessed (in 17%, n =11; 11%, n =7; and 12%, n=8 of studies, respectively). The location where studies were conducted, frequency of studies per country and the thematic addressed in the papers are presented in Figure 1.

Ninety-eight percent of the studies (n=60) addressed the access to water in schools. Information on water source was provided in total for 16,963 schools. Considering all settings, 66% of schools had an improved water source.

Eighty-eight percent of the papers (n=57) evaluated the sanitation services in schools. Sixty-four percent of the studies (n=41) described the type of sanitation facility found in the schools and 46% of the studies (n=30) informed the number of students per sanitation facility. In total, sanitation facilities were assessed in 16,960 schools. Considering all settings, 31% of schools had improved sanitation facilities.

Eighty-two percent of the papers (n=53) assessed the hygiene services at schools. Sixty percent (n=39) reported lack of soap, 35% (n=23) mentioned lack of handwashing facilities, 26% (n=17) indicated lack of water for handwashing, and 25% (n=16) informed lack of water inside the sanitation facilities in schools. Considering all settings, 37% of schools had handwashing facilities, 21% of schools had water available for handwashing, 19% of schools had soap and 11% of schools had water available in the sanitation facilities.

Pie chart represents the number of studies according to the location they were conducted. Minimum of 1 and maximum of 11.

Figure 1 Distribution of the 65 publications included in the systematic review according to the location the studies were conducted

4. Discussion

Hand hygiene is fundamental for the combat of COVID-19. However, handwashing cannot be practiced in schools lacking a water source or in schools with water available but not for hygiene purposes. The number of schools with water available for handwashing or inside the sanitation facilities was smaller than the number of schools with any type of water source (improved and unimproved), showing that the existence of the water supply in the school does not guarantee its use for hygiene practices.

The small number of handwashing stations in the schools might result in the congestion of the facilities. The literature indicates that handwashing with water alone reduces bacteria contamination on hands, and thus, the risk of water-related illness such as diarrhea (Burton et al., 2011). Notwithstanding, in the case of COVID-19, the presence of the soap is imperative. Due to its enveloped property, human coronaviruses pose low resistance to disinfectants (Chaudhary et al., 2020). Keeping that in mind, the WHO checklist recommends that schools should ensure adequate and sufficient supplies of soap and hand sanitizer (Benzian et al., 2020). However, only 19% of the schools (n=985) addressed in this review could comply with the WHO requirement regarding the presence of soap (not necessarily placed in the handwashing facilities). Lack of soap was the most frequent complaint across studies concerning hygiene (60%, n = 39), being mentioned even in schools with reported presence of soap.

Even though the fecal-oral route has not yet been proven to be one of the transmissions pathways for SARS-CoV-2, the water and sanitation conditions in the schools described by the studies pose an extra risk for the school community. Without the proper sewage treatment and subsequent disposal, the water sources in the schools are at risk of getting contaminated with the virus, thus, enabling waterborne transmission (Bhowmick et al., 2020). Due to the unsanitary state of the sanitation facilities in schools, with visible contamination of feces, students might also be at risk of water-washed transmission (i.e., touch their mouths, noses or eyes with contaminated hands) (Tian et al., 2020).

5. Conclusion

The human right to safe drinking water and sanitation and its normative contents have not been guaranteed in schools. Most of the schools (66%) reported to have an improved water source, whereas as for sanitation, only a small portion of schools (31%) had improved sanitation facilities. In the context of COVID-19 pandemic, the current school's infrastructure hampers students to practice handwashing, a fundamental strategy to contain the spread of SARS-CoV-2 among school communities. Even though the fecal-oral route has not yet been proven to be one of the transmissions pathways for SARS-CoV-2, the provision of WASH services in schools is essential for the prevention of COVID-19 and other water-related diseases in the school environment.

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